

BIOMIMETIC ORGANIC-INORGANIC COMPOSITE COATINGS FOR METAL IMPLANTS USED IN ORTHOPEDICS AND DENTISTRY. PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION

Helga Füredi Milhofer¹, Alon Elyada¹, Ronald Schade², Steffi Grohmann²,
Klaus Liefeith², Nissim Garti¹, Herbert P. Jennissen³

¹ Casali Center of Applied Chemistry, Institute of Chemistry, the Hebrew University of Jerusalem
90914 Jerusalem, Israel

E mails: helga@mail.huji.ac.il; alon87@gmail.com; garti@mail.huji.ac.il

² Department of Biomaterials, Institute for Bioprocessing and Analytical Measurement Techniques
(iba) e.V.

Rosenhof, 37308 Heilbad Heiligenstadt, Germany

Emails: ronald.schade@iba-heiligenstadt.de, steffi.grohmann@iba-heiligenstadt.de;
klaus.liefeith@iba-heiligenstadt.de ; web page: <http://www.iba-heiligenstadt.de>

³ Department of Biochemical Endocrinology, Institute of Physiological Chemistry, University of
Duisburg-Essen, Essen, Germany.

E mail: hp.jennissen@uni-due.de

Keywords: calcium phosphate, polyelectrolyte multilayers, coatings, mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

Biomimetic organic-inorganic composite coatings for metal implants, consisting of an organic matrix interspersed with calcium deficient carbonate apatite crystals have been prepared and characterized. The coatings were synthesized by first depositing the organic matrix in the form of polyelectrolyte multilayers, followed by incubation of the construct into a low supersaturation, metastable calcifying solution (MCS) to induce and sustain calcium phosphate crystallization. Single and/or mixed multilayers were constructed using layer by layer deposition of poly-L-lysine, (PLL) alternating with poly-L-glutamate, (PGA), poly-L- aspartate (PAA), and/or chondroitin sulfate (CS). Coatings were characterized by FTIR, XRD (not shown), SEM + EDX, AFM, CLSM and mechanical testing.

The PEMLs had a grainy topography with aggregate sizes increasing in the order: $(\text{PLL}/\text{PGA})_n < (\text{PLL}/\text{PAA})_n < (\text{PLL}/\text{CS})_n$. Multilayers. of $(\text{PLL}/\text{PGA})_n$ and $(\text{PLL}/\text{PAA})_n$ promoted, whereas $(\text{PLL}/\text{CS})_n$ slightly inhibited nucleation and early crystal growth of calcium phosphate. Generally, platelet-like crystals of calcium deficient carbonate apatite were obtained, their structure and morphology depending on the conditions of the MSC rather than on the composition of the underlying PEML. Force spectroscopy measurements with a colloid probe (AFM) show that calcification significantly increased the mechanical stiffness of the coating as compared to uncalcified PEML films. Calcified PEML coatings typically revealed Young's moduli in the range of 5 - 10 MPa, whereas earlier determined values for uncalcified PEML films were in the range of ~9 kPa [for $(\text{PLL}/\text{CS})_n$ films] to several hundred kPa [for $(\text{PLL}/\text{PGA})_n$ films].

After crystallization coatings were strongly attached to the underlying substrate as shown by standardized adhesive tape testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

In orthopedics and dentistry some metals and metal alloys are the material of choice as implants for load-bearing applications. However, although they may have excellent mechanical properties, most are bioinert and therefore difficult to integrate into the surrounding tissue. In order to facilitate biontegration, different surface modifications have been proposed, including precipitation of calcium

phosphates onto pretreated metal surfaces [1-3]. More recently attempts have been made to develop surface coatings which more closely resemble the natural material into which the implant has to integrate. Such approach involves close observation of the natural processes of bone and dentin biomineralization [4,5].

Bone and dentin are organic-inorganic composites with nanosized calcium phosphate crystals precisely aligned within an organic matrix, whose main component is collagen. In addition the extracellular matrix contains non-collageneous molecules such as proteoglycans and acidic proteins, the latter being actively involved in the mineralization process [5]. In osseogenesis the organic matrix is deposited first and is then calcified by matrix vesicles containing poorly crystallized calcium phosphate [6]. The above strategy has been emulated by us to synthesize organic-inorganic composite coatings for bioinert metal implants to improve their bioactivity and facilitate osseointegration [7-9].

An attractive, simple method to deposit an organic matrix on surfaces is the construction of polyelectrolyte multilayers, PEMs, by alternate adsorption of positively and negatively charged polyelectrolytes, respectively, as first proposed by Decher [10]. An isotope method was developed to follow the build-up of PEMs on metal surfaces [12]. Calcification of the thus deposited organic matrix may be achieved by immersion of the coated substrate into a metastable calcifying solution (MCS, [9]) in which case nucleation of calcium phosphate crystals is initiated by the functional groups of the organic matrix. Alternatively, in the process of buildup of the organic matrix, amorphous calcium phosphate particles (ACP) are co-adsorbed as nucleating sites [7, 8], which, upon immersion into MCS, become initiators of crystal growth. The capacity of the organic matrix to induce bone may be enhanced by co-adsorbing bioactive molecules, such as BMP-2 [11, 12]. Other drugs, such as antibiotics, calcitonin, etc, may also be immobilized within the multilayers and then locally released at the place of implant fixation.

In this presentation we review some of our recent research on the preparation and properties of organic-inorganic composites and include new results on their interfacial morphology and viscoelastic properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Chemicals and substrates: Analytical grade chemicals and tridistilled water (TDW) were used for all experiments. The following polymers were purchased from Sigma and/or Alamanda Polymers (Huntsville AL, USA): poly-L-lysine (PLL), Mw 30–70 KDa, poly-L-glutamic acid (PGA), Mw 50–100 KDa, poly-L-aspartic acid (PAA) Mw 5–15 KDa, and chondroitin sulfate (CS), from bovine cartilage, Mw 15–40 kDa. All polymers were used as received. Solutions of PE at 1 mg/mL in HEPES buffer, adjusted to pH 8.0 were freshly prepared not longer than 1 day before use. Calcium chloride and sodium phosphate stock solutions were prepared by dissolving the required amount of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck) and Na_2HPO_4 (BDH), in TDW. The pH of the sodium phosphate stock solution was adjusted by HCl to the required value (pH 8.0). Each of the stock solutions contained, in addition, 0.05% sodium azide to prevent bacterial contamination.

As substrates glass plates (Borofloat 33 from Schott, Jena, Germany) and/or ultrahydrophilic sandblasted, acid etched titanium miniplates (Ti-SLA plates, custom made after [13] by courtesy of MorphoPlant GmbH, Bochum, Germany) were used.

2.2. Sample preparation: Organic - inorganic coatings were prepared as described in [9]. Briefly, the organic matrix was deposited on glass or titanium surfaces in the form of PEMs, employing layer by layer deposition of polyelectrolytes with alternating charges [10]. Single or mixed PEMs were thus constructed from poly-L-lysine, (PLL) alternating with poly-L-glutamate, (PGA), poly-L-aspartate (PAA), and/or chondroitin sulfate (CS). In some samples a first layer of polyethylene imine (PEI) was added to enhance adherence of the PEML to the substrate. The exact compositions of the respective PEMs are given in the results section. At the end of the adsorption process, the plates were washed with TDW, air dried and kept refrigerated for at least 12 h before further use in order to allow the multilayer to stabilize.

In the second step the coated substrate was incubated at 25⁰ C in a metastable calcifying solution (MCS). The solution was prepared by mixing equal volumes of calcium chloride and sodium phosphate solutions (Ca/P atomic ratio 1.6) in HEPES buffer, pH 8, and was filtered before use. During the incubation period calcium phosphate crystal deposition was initiated by the PEML and crystals grew on account of the respective ions in the MCS. The initial supersaturation for each experiment is given in the results section. The supersaturation is expressed as

$$\sigma = (IP_{1/n} - Ksp_{1/n}) / Ksp_{1/n} \quad (1)$$

where IP is the ionic product, Ksp is the solubility product, and n is the number of ions in the formula unit of the particular calcium phosphate phase.

In some samples, following the completion of the final crystal layer, the construct was covered with an additional polyelectrolyte multilayer.

2.3. Characterization of the substrates and coatings: Coatings were characterized by FTIR, XRD (not shown), AFM, CLSM, SEM + EDX and mechanical testing.

Imaging: Substrates coated with PEMLs were imaged and characterized by atomic force microscopy in the tapping mode (AFM; Scanning Probe Microscope from Veeco/Bruker, Santa Barbara CA, USA) and by confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM; Confocal microscope from Leica Microsystems, Mannheim, Germany). For AFM analysis the plates were used as is, while for CLSM analysis the plates were wetted with TDW before observation.

Imaging of calcium phosphate crystals was performed by HR-SEM (Sirion and/or XHRSEM Magellan 400L, both from FEI company, Hillsboro Oregon, USA) with EDX attachments for elemental analysis. Before analysis, glass samples were coated with a gold-palladium layer, whereas Ti-SLA samples were directly imaged.

Determination of viscoelastic properties after [14]: Samples were mounted in a fluidic cell and allowed to equilibrate in buffer for 30 min. With the CellHesion AFM (JPK, Berlin, Germany) force maps of 100 x 100 μm² were recorded employing cantilevers that were equipped with glass spheres (diameter 11 μm, spring constant was determined to be 63.4 mN/m). Force distance curves were measured after reaching a set point of 1.9 nN for an indentation of 200 nm (speed of 8 μm/s, afterwards cantilevers were retracted from the polymer film to z= 4 μm above the sample surface before starting a new measurement). The slope of the force distance curves was obtained through a curve fitting procedure and plotted as a stiffness map of the sample surface (all employing the JPK software). Finally, the obtained stiffness values were transformed into Young's moduli employing the modified Hertz sphere model, as described in reference [14].

Adhesive tape test: Adhesion of the coating to the substrate surface was tested according to the ASTM protocol [15]. An adhesive tape (Elcometer) was placed over the coating and then pulled off. Before and after the procedure the surface was imaged by HR-SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Topography of uncalcified PEML coatings: The topography of different PEMLs was assessed by AFM and CSLM. A grainy texture with fairly uniform grains was revealed for all investigated PEM films as shown in Figure 1(see also refs. [9, 14]).

The grain sizes depended on the type of the anionic layer, increasing in the succession: PGA < PAA < CS [9]. This sequence is to be expected, since (PLL/PGA)_n multilayers have been found to adsorb in the β-sheet conformation, while (PLL/PAA)_n multilayers adsorb as random coil [16 - 18]. Since GAGs form highly hydrated PEM assemblies, PLL/CS multilayers are expected to form the biggest aggregates on surfaces [19].

Figure 1: CLSM and AFM (a2) micrographs of different polymer layers on glass: (a1) (PLL/PGA)₁₀-PLL^{FITC}; (a2) (PLL/PGA)₁₀ (10μm x 10μm) (b) (PLL/PAA)₇-PLL^{FITC}; (c) (PLL/CS)₇-PLL^{FITC}.

3.2 Crystallization induced by PEMPLs: Crystals grown upon immersion of the coated substrates into MCS were imaged by AFM (Fig. 2b) and HR-SEM (Fig.3) and identified by FTIR and XRD spectroscopy [9]. Fig. 2b shows that the crystals closely follow the topography of the underlying polymer (Fig. 2a). Kinetic studies [9] show a significant influence of the composition and structure of the PEMPL on the rate of calcium phosphate nucleation, the efficiency of crystallization induction increasing in the following order

$$(PLL/CS)_{10} < \text{uncoated glass} \sim [(PLL/PGA)_5(PLL/CS)_5] < (PLL/PAA)_{10} \\ \sim [(PLL/PGA)_5(PLL/PAA)_5] < (PLL/PGA)_{10} \ll \text{HAP powder}$$

Here uncoated glass is the negative and hydroxyapatite powder the positive control, respectively. The above sequence correlates well with the molecular structure of the adsorbed PEMPLs (see above) indicating that calcium phosphate nucleation is indeed initiated by the polymer facing the MCS. The mechanism might be similar to the one envisaged by Addadi et al [20] for calcite crystal nucleation by assemblies of organic macromolecules.

In contrast to the nucleation kinetics, the crystal morphology, composition and structure were determined by the composition of the MCS rather than by the composition or structure of the underlying polymer assembly. In most cases calcium deficient carbonate apatites with a platelet-like morphology (Fig. 3) and Ca/P atomic ratios between 1.35 and 1.45 were obtained (for more details see ref. [9]).

Figure 2: Glass plates coated with PEI-PAA (PLL/PAA)₅ (a) before and (b) after two weeks incubation in MCS are imaged by AFM in tapping mode (5 μm x 5 μm images). Conditions of calcification: pH 8, $\sigma_{\text{HAP}} = 16.1$, $\sigma_{\text{TCP}} = 0.32$ (α -TCP).

When coatings were applied to Ti-SLA plates, both uncalcified and calcified coatings adopted the substrate contours, leaving the porousness of the substrate intact [9]. Thus, with the pores preserved, integration of rough, coated substrates into the surrounding tissue should be facilitated.

3,3 Mechanical properties In order to assess the elastic modulus of the organic-inorganic composites two types of systems were prepared on glass substrates, system A with a crystal top layer and system B with the crystals covered with an additional PEML:

A : (PLL-PGA)₉-(PLL-PAA) - CaP and

B : (PLL-PGA)₉-(PLL-PAA) – CaP – (PLL-PGA)₄-(PLL-CS)

Figure 3: HR-SEM micrograph of calcium phosphate crystals grown on a glass plate coated with (PLL/PAA)₆; magn. x 50 000; Ca/P = 1.50. The morphology is typical for crystals grown from MCS of pH 8, initial Ca/P = 1.6, ionic strength 0.09 - 1.0.

The systems were analyzed by means of force spectroscopy with colloidal probes, (AFM). Typical force distance curves for the samples A and B are presented in figure 4. At a tip-sample separation of 0 nm the colloidal probe is in contact with the sample surface. When the cantilever is then indented into the sample, its vertical deflection corresponds to the force that is exerted to elastically deform the coating. The slope of a force distance curve can be transformed into the respective Young's modulus employing the modified Hertz sphere model [14]. The results are approximately 10 MPa for sample A and 5 MPa for sample B, respectively.

The force distance curves of the coatings with PEM covered CaP crystals (sample B) typically display slopes with a lower steepness than the ones obtained from uncovered CaP nanocrystals (sample A). However, the differences in the Young's moduli of uncovered and PEM covered CaP crystals are relatively small, when compared to uncalcified PEML coatings [14]. It is of interest to point out that calcification tremendously increased the mechanical stiffness when compared to the uncalcified PEM films. Before calcification PEM assemblies typically reveal Young's moduli in the range of ~9 kPa (CS films, [14]) to several hundred kPa (PGA films). With the determined Young's modulus of almost 10 MPa for sample A the calcification leads to an increase of the films stiffness of up to 1000 fold.

Figure 4: Typical force distance curves obtained for the organic-inorganic nanocomposite coatings by means of force spectroscopy with colloidal probes. The respective slopes were determined by fitting the curves and were subsequently transformed into Young's moduli employing the modified Hertz sphere model [14]. Sample A, uncovered CaP crystals: (PLL-PGA)₉-(PLL-PAA) - CaP and sample B, PEM covered CaP crystals: (PLL-PGA)₉-(PLL-PAA) - CaP - (PLL-PGA)₄-(PLL-CS).

The strength of adhesion of organic - inorganic composite coatings to the substrate, as assessed by the ASTM test [15] is superior. In contrast to calcium phosphate crystals grown directly on glass surfaces [9] and/ or to the adhesion of PEMLs - amorphous calcium phosphate coatings [7], which are easily removed by the adhesive tape, the removal of crystalline calcium phosphate layers grown "in situ" upon and within calcium phosphate multilayers was negligible [7,9]. This feature may be especially important in dental implantology, where the implant is screwed into the bone tissue of the jaw.

Preliminary "in vitro" cell culture studies (not shown) indicate that coatings with crystal top layers are not conducive to cell spreading and proliferation, which compares well with our previous experience with octacalcium phosphate crystals as top layer in similar systems [7, 8]. However, it was noteworthy to observe that the alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity of MC3T3-E1 cells, as an early marker for osteogenic differentiation was not inhibited.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The formation and mechanical characteristics of organic–inorganic composite coatings on smooth (glass) and rough (Ti-SLA) surfaces have been studied. The composite consists of polyelectrolyte multilayers (PEMLs) within and above which calcium phosphate crystals grow upon immersion of the polymer-coated substrate into a metastable calcifying solution (MCS). The build-up of the PEMLs on rough titanium surfaces appears to be very similar to that on glass and they exhibit a very high stability [12]. The rate of calcium phosphate nucleation depends on the composition and molecular structure of the polymer assembly, while the crystal composition and structure is determined by the conditions of precipitation (composition of the MCS, pH, temperature, time of aging, etc). Calcification of the PEMLs dramatically increases the stiffness of the coatings (about 1000 fold), as demonstrated by force spectroscopy with a colloidal probe. Mechanical tests according to an ASTM protocol also show that the composite coatings tightly adhere to the underlying substrate, which may be of special significance in dental surgery, where the implant is screwed into the bone tissue. The above results point to a simple, cost effective method for the preparation of organic - inorganic composite coatings to increase the bioactivity of metal orthopedic and dental implants.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support granted by the German–Israeli Foundation (GIF, grant I-907-39, 3/2006) is gratefully acknowledged.

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